

NONVERBAL USABILITY TESTS WITH EMOTIONS FOR THE VISUALLY IMPAIRED

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes a research-in-progress on the use of onomatopoeias as an alternative form of the EMOCARD. Initially, the theoretical foundations are established in order to identify the most relevant senses when constructing spatial representations for the blind: tactile sense, haptic senses and verbal language. The DECIDE framework was used to define the research subjects, the timing, the research instrument and the evaluation paradigm. The research defined several onomatopoeias for the EMOCARD face images, and all suggestions were recorded to enable an evaluation of the relationship between the images and the onomatopoeias. The research started at the beginning of February 2014, and has been ongoing until now the present moment. Hence, as yet, no conclusions have been reached.

KEYWORDS: *usability test with emotions; spatial representation; onomatopoeias*

INTRODUCTION

Accessibility in Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) is necessary in order to make users feel comfortable, thus, increasing browsing time and encouraging their return to the environment. So that computer interfaces may become more accessible, evaluations are carried out at several different points in time, from the design stage through to implementation and operation. Researchers have at least four paradigms at their disposal for these evaluations (Nielsen, 1999): Specialist Inspections, Computerized Procedures, Heuristic Evaluations and Usability Testing. Of the four paradigms, only usability testing evaluates interaction with the users. The research reported in this article describes an experiment to identify the onomatopoeias that best represent images of emotions. The first usability test was conducted in 2011 using AVEA WebGD, an environment previously evaluated by other paradigms. Twelve blind male/female research subjects (with no other disabilities), participated in the study and, after a period of adjustment, efficiency tests and questionnaires were applied in order to time task execution and user satisfaction (BERG, 2011). A number of barriers were encountered and repaired.

In the search for usability tests with emotions (BERG, 2012), the EMOCARD was identified and used for a new series of

tests. Twelve deaf male/female research subjects (with no other disabilities) were selected. After executing the tasks, seven questions were asked regarding navigation and accessibility in a HCI. Using EMOCARD, barriers regarding colors and the general feeling of the environment were identified (Berg, 2013). These results provided a broader knowledge regarding usability testing with the use of the researchers' emotions.

However, many usability tests of this kind are based on images, which presents a natural barrier for people with visual disabilities. Thus, there is a need to develop tools that allow the visually impaired to participate in usability testing with the use of emotions. Therefore, this paper proposes to determine whether the images of emotions presented by EMOCARD may include versions for the blind, through human feelings. The research question to be addressed concerns the validation of onomatopoeia; "Can onomatopoeias correspond to the emotions encountered in the images of EMOCARD"?

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

By understanding the importance of including persons with disabilities, this study has sought to conceptualize two main

sections that interact and complement one another: tests using emotions and spatial representations. Since the study is focused on testing a method, theoretical questions regarding accessibility and the visually impaired will not be discussed

Tests using Emotions

Salovey and Meyer (1990) contend that emotions are organized responses. Responses occur after crossing the borders of several different systems: psychological, cognitive, motivational and experimental. Emotions typically arise as a response to an event, whether internal or external, and which possess positive or negative valenced meanings (SALOVEY & MEYER, 1990).

Agarwal and Meyer (2009) argue that users have qualitative emotional experiences when they use a product or interface. These emotions are not only central for users to judge the totality of experiences, but can also affect the way users perceive usability (AGARWAL & MEYER, 2009).

For Walker and Prytherch (2008), motivated users demonstrate less anxiety, a greater perception of their self-efficacy and they adopt more positive attitudes. Thus, there is a need to develop interfaces with greater positive emotional responses. To meet this need, models should seek friendliness through emotional interaction, bringing mechanical application interfaces closer to the way in which humans communicate with each other (TZVETANOVA, TANG & JUSTICE, 2007).

The cognitive theory as proposed by Ortony, Clore and Collins (1988) defines emotions as positively or negatively "valenced" reactions to situations, consisting of events, objects and actors. Ancker, Kukafka and Chan (2012) describe emotional responses as negative, positive, or mixed. Moreover, they also claim that in user evaluation, adaptive interfaces exert more positively valenced emotions (TZVETANOVA, TANG & JUSTICE, 2007).

HCI emotional evaluations, using non-verbal methods to identify emotions during a human-computer interaction, are useful for identifying barriers to an interface. Nonverbal tools adopted in order to valence environments were developed by Desmet and Hekkert (2003), who stated that emotions are difficult to verbalize, due to the cognitive effort used to express them. This leads to them losing their content in the same way as a translation process.

Literature review

In 2013, Flores *et al* undertook a systematic literature review involving the most significant papers on the issue of spatial representation in both the blind and the sighted. In the databases - IEEE, SCOPUS; SPRINGER; UFSC Library, CAPES and the Portal Web of Knowledge four combined keywords were employed. The keywords were "blind", "spatial representation", "spatial figure" and "3D", which initially generated 10,823 articles. Following certain constraints, such as "full text", "sanctioned by CAPES", "containing one of the keywords in the title" and "reading the abstracts" demonstrated

relevance and eliminated duplicates, leaving a total of seven relevant articles. Table 2 demonstrates the extracted articles, the first author and the year of publication.

1st Author	Title	Year
AFONSO, Amandine	Structural properties of spatial representations in blind people	2010
HABER, Ralph Norman	Properties of spatial representations	1993
LANDAU, Barbara	Spatial Knowledge and Geometric Representation	1981
LANDAU, Barbara	Spatial Representation of Objects	1989
MILLAR, Susanna	Spatial Representation by Blind and Sighted Children	1976
SCHMIDT, Susanna	Spatial representations in blind people	2012
TESHIMA, Yoshinori	Three-Dimensional Tactile Models	2010

Table 2 – Extracted articles.. Source: Berg and Ulbricht, 2013
The seven studies identified a total of 112 concepts, in which the most frequently identified keyword was "blind" (69). No results were obtained for the keyword "spatial figure". Table 3 indicates the quantities of concepts for four key words identified for each publication.

CONCEPTS	QUANTITY PER ARTICLE							SUB-TOTAL
	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	
BLIND	23	8	14	1	10	3	10	69
SPATIAL REPRESENTATION	16	6	4	0	8	1	5	40
SPATIAL FIGURE	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3D	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	3
TOTAL	39	14	18	4	18	4	15	112

Table 3 – Quantity of concepts identified by author
Note: Haber – A1; Afonso – A2; Schmidt – A3; Teshima – A4; Landau – A5; Landau *et al* – A6 and Millar – A7
Source: the authors, 2013

Spatial Representations

Spatial Representation (SR) is basically the ability of the human brain to use metaphors to build knowledge and to form relationships with the world. The study of SR began with research focused on the psychology of memory in both sighted and blind subjects (HABER *et al*, 1993). According to Afonso (2010), spatial representation appears to include valid metric information, and studies consistent with Haber *et al* (1993) have demonstrated that representations made by children incorporate certain geometric properties.

Studies in other areas of cognition have revealed a rich system of spatial knowledge in blind children (LANDAU, 1989). A review of Landau, Spelke and Gleitman (1984) encountered evidence regarding knowledge of spatial layout. The study also revealed haptic skills and spatial representations of objects that went beyond simple maps (LANDAU, 1989), as well as an excellent knowledge of spatial language.

From the viewpoint of Berkeley (1993), haptic patterns or exploratory motor coordination serve as a basis for the unified development of the spatial representations of objects. Landau (1989) corroborates this idea when he argues that blind children naturally develop haptic exploratory activities, which allow them to extract important information from objects. Teshima (2010) believes that the blind are able to recognize three-dimensional shapes through haptic sensations. Moreover, this not only involves visual information, but also the use of haptic sensations, which help to improve recognition in 3D, thus enabling the construction of SR from objects.

The implications of using different strategies to process spatial information are important when spatial information is obtained from spoken language, as is often the case in the blind (SCHMIDT *et al*, 2012). Millar (1976) assumes that the differences in spatial representation cannot be inferred because it is necessary to adopt a verbal strategy rather than strategic imagery to process the information available, as in the case of the blind.

However, research has demonstrated that representations made by children incorporate certain geometrical properties (HABER *et al*, 1993), as well as evidence of the knowledge of spatial layout (LANDAU, SPELKE & GLEITMAM, 1984). The main elements for generating SR include valid metric information (Afonso, 2010), haptic skills and spatial representations of objects (LANDAU, 1989).

Haptic Sensations

The haptic system is the result of tactile-kinesthetic coordination efforts made during exploratory acts, primarily used in the manipulation of objects with the aim of detecting size, shapes, textures, etc. (MAUERBERG-DECASTRO, 2004). Ochaita and Rose (1995) presented the haptic system or active touch, as the most important sensory system for the blind to discover the world. The authors make a distinction between the haptic proprioceptive and the haptic visual systems. The first provides fluency to coordinated actions through joint muscle synergies. The second key aspect of this approach relates to the immediate postural responses during action (and at rest) (i.e., low-order system).

Then, there is the visual system that, in addition to the underlying functions of the haptic system, detects depth because of binocular disparity, motion parallax, texture gradient and shadows (ATKINS, FISHER & JACOBS, 2001). Finally, the haptic visual system does not replace the haptic proprioceptive system, it acts at a high-order level that guides movements towards the visualized targets.

Based on these studies, touch becomes more important for the formation of SR, especially since it contributes to the construction of mental maps and geometric shapes. The study also brought to light the importance of haptic sensations in this composition.

Onomatopoeias

One of the problems with research is the limitation of usability tests including emotions that use images, which clearly creates barriers for people with visual impairments. In the pursuit of solving this problem, research conducted on spatial representations in the blind have identified touch and haptic sensations as the main sources for the development of SR. It is assumed that even sound stimuli compose haptic sensations (MILLAR, 1976).

The use of spoken language is also indicated as a component for the creation of SR. Therefore, in order to develop adaptations of usability tests including emotions, such as Emocard, for use by people with visual impairments, touch may be considered as a way to recreate the tool. However, a second approach may be based on spoken language. The limitation of language, in this case, is the same as indicated in cases of verbal usability tests, and cognitive effort is required to translate and understand its meaning and content, and onomatopoeia may be used.

Onomatopoeic sound reproduction is in the form of phonemes and, in general, they are universally understood. Animal sounds, noises, screams and sounds of nature or machines can replace the name (verb) or the SR of any particular thing. Table 4 demonstrates some examples:

ONOMATOPOEIA	EXAMPLE
Boom	Onomatopoeia of an explosion
Moo	Onomatopoeia of a cow
Vrum	Onomatopoeia of an accelerating car
Aiii	Onomatopoeia of pain (Portuguese)

Table 4 - Examples of onomatopoeia
Font: the authors, 2014

Developing a tactile model implies high costs and long waiting periods, and considering its importance, this model should be explored in depth in further articles. In this study, the onomatopoeic perspective will be addressed through the low costs involved and the facility with which the model may be developed.

Hence, between September and December 2013, a survey was conducted among graduate Design students at the Universidade Federal do Paraná and Engineering and Knowledge Management students at the Universidade, totaling twenty-nine research subjects. Subjects were shown a table containing eight emotions from the Emocard in the form of illustrations. Research subjects were requested to suggest onomatopoeias for each of the emotions listed.

Distress	Displeasure	Depression	Slipiness	Arousal	Relaxation	Pleasure	Excitement
aaaah	humf	oh	hm	oh	zii	heheh	haha
aaaah	HUMPF	Ooow	hmm	oh	zzz	HEHEHE	haha!
aarr	humpf	oum	hmm	oh	zzzz!	hehehe	HAHAHA
Aff./ Grr...	hunf	ouuu	hmmm...	OH!	zzzzz	hehehe	hahaha
ah!	hunf	ow	HUM	oh!	zzzzz	hehehehe	Hahaha!
ahhh	hunf		hummm	ohh		hihi	Hahaha!!
ahhhh			HUMMM	ohh		hihihi...	hahaha...
ahhhh...			Hummm...	ohhhh			hahshah
AHHHHH			huuum	OHHHH			hahahah
			nnnnn	ooh			HAHAHA
			uhmmm	oohh			hahshaha
			un	OHHH			HAHAHAH
			un...	ooo			lahshaha
			unhh	ooch			kkkkk
				ooch			kkkkkk
				ooch			kkkkkk
				Oooh!!!			kkkkkkk
				óóóó			
				ooouu			

Table #5 - Images, words and onomatopoeias
Source: adapted from Desmet, 2003

The responses generated a map with 89 different onomatopoeias, where the most similar were grouped for recording. Table 5 presents the images of the Emocard emotions, the name selected for the emotion and the onomatopoeias selected for recording.

With this information, similar onomatopoeias were grouped, and in conjunction with an audio producer, the onomatopoeias to be recorded were defined. The onomatopoeias were recorded one by one in an audio studio, in male and female voices for testing.

Methodology

This was a qualitative research that sought initial information concerning the problem. The DECIDE framework, as proposed by Preece, Rogers and Sharp (2002) was used to structure the research. DECIDE is the acronym for:

- Determine the goals,
- Explore the questions,
- Choose the evaluation paradigm,
- Identify the practical issues,
- Decide how to deal with ethical questions and
- Evaluate.

The goal was to verify whether the recreation of the Emocard tool using onomatopoeias may be recognized. The question

to be addressed concerned validation of the onomatopoeia. The research question was: "Can onomatopoeias correspond to the emotions encountered in the images of EMOCARD"?

The evaluation paradigm was a questionnaire. Validation was conducted by comparing the recorded onomatopoeias with the images from the EMOCARD. The evaluation was carried out by numbering the Emocard with the number of onomatopoeias that most resembled the emotion. As a research tool, an answer sheet was created for responses. An identification profile of the research subject was placed at the top informing gender, age and graduate program. Below this, for each voice type, an Emocard was printed in order to mark the answers. Illustration 1 presents a facsimile of the search tool.

Practical issues refer to defining the research subjects and the manner of applying the research. With regard to the research subjects, the Nielsen and Loranger (2007) recommendations were observed, by using five to twelve research subjects. The reasons for using this number of subjects were related to costs (LORANGER & NIELSEN, 2007), and the implementation schedule (PREECE, ROGERS & SHARP, 2002), so as to avoid a repetition of the results (NIELSEN & LORANGER, 2007). Thus, once the mapped recommendations were met, two groups were selected: one male and one female, made up of post-graduate students.

Figure 1 – Research tool facsimile.
Source: adapted from Desmet, 2003

The study was applied using the following steps:

1. Presentation of the research objectives and methodology
2. Presentation of the research tool to the research subjects
3. Playing all onomatopoeias, twice, with one short interval
4. Playing each onomatopoeia individually three times
5. Period for annotation of the onomatopoeia on the Emocard
6. Playing other onomatopoeias, one by one, repeating steps 3 and 4.
7. Collecting cards, thanks and finalization of the study.

Finally, in relation to ethical issues, researchers informed the research subjects that the object of evaluation was the tool and not themselves. It was also made clear that anonymity would be maintained, and that only information regarding gender, age and post-graduate study would be requested.

After collecting the cards, results were tabulated, and thus the number of recognitions for each onomatopoeia was identified.

RESULTS

The scientific lens of this research aimed to present the current situation of evaluating the human-computer interface of virtual learning environments. The usability test of the EMOCARD emotions was introduced for this type of assessment and knowledge regarding spatial representation in the blind.

Knowledge concerning spatial representations defined the sensations that the blind use: touch, hearing and the haptic - the component of spatial representations. Ochaita and Rose (1995) also demonstrated that, regardless of disability, the blind construct spatial representations in the same way as the sighted, but using other strategies.

This study used onomatopoeias, the representation of sound in the form of phonemes, which are generally universally understood. Based on the EMOCARD, the post-graduate students proposed onomatopoeias for each of the eight emotions, which were ordered, grouped and recorded in the studio with male and female voices.

The onomatopoeias were tested in March 2014, with the participation of six females and four males, and tabulated. Tabulation enabled us to verify and validate the onomatopoeias that represented the images of EMOCARD emotions. The most cited onomatopoeia was the one referring to “relaxation”, and it was recognized six times. “Sleepiness” received five recognitions and “arousal”, four. “Distress”, “excitement” and “pleasure” were recognized respectively by three, two and one subjects. “Depression” and “discontent” were not recognized by any subject.

Differences in perception were noted between men and women. “Affliction” was recognized only by women and “excitement” only by men. “Relaxation” and “sleepiness” received the same number of recognitions amongst males and females. The other onomatopoeias, due to few recognitions, did not permit evaluation.

As an exploratory research, this study has allowed us to answer the question “Can onomatopoeias correspond to the emotions encountered in the images of EMOCARD”? The statement is partially true because two onomatopoeias were recognized by most subjects and, with the exception of “depression” and “discontent”, all presented some kind of recognition.

At this point, the research should set out to follow two paths. The first: to increase evaluations to a statistical level. The second: to develop onomatopoeias, so that those which remained unrecognized may become recognizable.

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